

**ENTREPRENEURIAL TEACHING OR ENTREPRENEURIAL TRAINING: WHICH
APPROACH FOR YOUTH EMPOWERMENT IN NIGERIA**

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship as a concept is part of the curriculum in use in Nigerian education policy. The take up and proper implementation for the development of entrepreneurial skills and mindset raise so many questions including effective teaching methodology. The content provides much pedagogy that will result to producing graduates with skills, mindset, and confidence to explore, identify, develop and sustain business of their own rather than waiting for job. In this respect are institutions to teach or to train for students' entrepreneurial competence? Though teaching and training are closely related but there is *thin blue line* that makes the differences. The paper looks into the two terms to make a clear pathway on how to achieve the objectives of infusing entrepreneurship as a concept into the education system. The paper is of the opinion for 6 to 12 months extension to all final year students across all faculties/departments in all tertiary institutions where they are to undergo for extensive entrepreneurial training including lecture delivery from experts, excursion, preparing feasibility report of live business and to be submitted for assessment as condition for their graduation.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial, Training, Teaching, Live Business, Proposal, Assessment

Introduction

Education is a tool for change in behaviour. Individuals use the education they have received to enhance their knowledge and skills in identifying opportunities around them, which justifies that learning has taken place. Adıgüzel and Musluhittinoğlu (2021) opine that education enables individuals to develop their sense of freedom, self-control, and self-confidence, so does it also allow individuals to discover and experience different career paths. High quality education is an important factor in inciting creativity in young people. One of the most important aspects of education is that it prepares students for their future careers. Do Paço et al. in Adıgüzel and Musluhittinoğlu (2021) opine that one criterion necessary to being successful is the ability to put the knowledge and skills one has learned to practice. Lacking these qualities by our graduates are the leading factors to redundancy resulting to unemployment. Problem of unemployment among graduates can be linked to their inability to think of alternative career path different from their academic pursuit.

Hence, students need these abilities to guide them in identifying a career path inform of entrepreneurial mindset in their area of specialization for them to see bright future after graduation. Entrepreneurship is more than business management. Inegbenebor in Akpan (2021) believes that “entrepreneurship studies education is a problem-solving approach to students’ empowerment that is capable of leading them to gain the skills required to plan, start, run and grow a business that focuses on innovation and development of new products and services”. This is different from what others think of entrepreneurship as business management to be handled by teachers/lecturers of business schools, department or faculty.

The inclusion of entrepreneurship as a concept in the educational curriculum resulted from the belief that the problem of unemployment among graduates will be a bygone issue taking into

consideration what scholars tabled. By its nature entrepreneurship education is crucial in Nigeria as it helps addressing unemployment, fosters innovation, and promotes economic diversification. Entrepreneurship education is expected to promote innovation, creativity, and problem-solving skills, and leading to the development of new products and services. There are abundant business opportunities in our societies being Nigerians are naturally entrepreneurial.

The inclusion of entrepreneurship education in the curriculum makes turnaround of the focus and hope of the nation to address the problem of unemployment among the graduates. This is because entrepreneurship study according to Paul in Akpan (2021) posits that “to provide the graduate youths with enough training and support that will enable them to establish a career in small and medium scale businesses”. Upon this assertion Akpan (2021) buttresses that “entrepreneurship education was introduced to provide students in tertiary institutions with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of ventures” this is an addition to offer functional education for youths that will enable them to be self-employed and self-reliant. However, handling entrepreneurship education brings in many issues arising on how to deliver it to students for entrepreneurial competency.

Entrepreneurial skills and mindset are activity-based pedagogies that are essential in training individual to be conversant with the concept for applicability. Therefore, what method is the most suitable to handle entrepreneurship in our institutions; is to teach or to train? According to the law dictionary online 2nd edition training is “organized activity aiming at imparting instructions and information that will improve the recipient’s performance or to reach a level of skill or knowledge” while teaching according to Amidon in Rajagopalan (2019) is an interactive process, primarily involving classroom talk which takes place between teacher and pupil and occurs during definable activities”. According to Concise Oxford Dictionary 10th edition define training as “teach a

particular skill or type of behaviour through a regular practice and instruction” while teaching “impart knowledge to or instruct (someone) in how to do something especially in a school or as part of recognized programme.” It is necessary for a particular job or activity and is highly practical and performance-oriented. It focuses on enabling individuals to perform specific tasks efficiently and effectively (Dutt, 2024).

Literature Review

Differences between Teaching and Training

Although teaching and training go along with many occasions, there are slight differences between these two processes. Dutt (2024) in a blog posits that “the differences between teaching and training consist, of *fine line* and recognizing it can lead to more effective educational strategies and hence better outcome. Furthermore, he opines that

Teaching is traditionally linked with imparting knowledge. It develops understanding and further foster critical thinking. It is about broadening the horizon of learners, often in academic settings. While training is more about skill acquisition and proficiency, it is usually with specific goal or task in mind often in professional or vocational context.

Professionally, both aim to educate participants, but their specific goals vary. Teachers typically focus on preparing students for careers by equipping them with critical thinking skills. By developing broad knowledge, students can pursue field of their interests and natural talents. Conversely, training strives to prepare participants to complete a certain task. *Indeed* (2023) a professional platform expatiates further that

Teaching is an instructional method that promotes students' theoretical understanding of a subject. Teachers usually educate their students in a classroom setting and encourage critical thinking. Training is an instructional method that prepares a person to complete a specific task. Trainers use a practical approach and allow participants to gain practice by guiding them through hands-on assignments.

Basically, teaching mainly involves theory, whereas training involves a practical approach to acquire skill. Teaching is for gaining knowledge while training is to develop skill, competence and mindset; usually the later came after the former. Training ends with imparting necessary skills and other required characteristics for particular career. Although teaching and training go along with many occasions, there are slight differences between these two processes. Basically, teaching mainly involves theory, whereas training involves a practical approach (Anuradha, 2022). He adds that “teaching can be described as the sharing of knowledge or giving instructions on how to do something. This process mainly involves teachers or instructors. Primarily, the process of teaching is associated with classrooms, where theoretical knowledge is provided”. He however further elaborates that “teaching helps to develop the intellectual growth of students.

According to a professional organization *GeeksforGeeks* (2024) “teaching is a process of facilitating learning, knowledge acquisition, and skill development in individuals through various instructional methods and techniques.” From this it outlines certain features associated with teaching, thus;

- **Imparting Knowledge:** The primary goal of teaching is to impart knowledge and understanding to students. This involves explaining concepts, theories, principles, and facts related to a particular subject or topic.
- **Facilitating Learning:** Teaching aims at facilitating the learning process by providing guidance, support, and resources to help students grasp and internalize new information.
- **Promoting Critical Thinking:** Effective teaching encourages critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and analytical reasoning among students (GeeksforGeeks, 2024).

For training, it is a process by which attitudes, skills, and capabilities to do a particular job are increased. It is a process of learning new skills and applying knowledge. Similarly certain features are shown to understand training, these include:

- **Skill Development:** Developing practical skills and competencies that are directly relevant to performing tasks or responsibilities associated with a particular job or role. This can include technical skills, interpersonal skills and problem-solving abilities
- **Practical Application:** Emphasis on hands-on practice, application, and experiential learning to reinforce learning and build proficiency.
- **Task-Oriented Approach:** Adopts a task-oriented approach, focusing on the specific tasks, activities, or responsibilities required for successful job performance. It aims to bridge the gap between current skills and desired competencies. (GeeksforGeeks, 2024)

With the foregone analyses, one can understand that teaching is more of transmitting knowledge and improving the cognitive domain, whereas training is about developing skill, improving performance ability, creating resilience and competency to demonstrate and conduct a given task efficiently and effectively and this is what entrepreneurial is all aiming at for the students.

Entrepreneurship or Entrepreneurial Education as a Learning Concept

Entrepreneurship or entrepreneurial as a programme is part of the approved curriculum in Nigerian tertiary institutions and even bring down to secondary schools level. Teaching entrepreneurship raised conflicting views on whether entrepreneurs are born or made through education and training and to certain extent remain unresolved. Prochazkoba (2015) maintains that “at the current time perhaps the majority of scholars and universities believe that entrepreneurship can and should be taught”. Matlay in Amadi-Echendu et al (2016) poses that “entrepreneurship education represents an efficient and cost-effective way of increasing the number and quality of enterprising graduates

entering the economy”. Shikalepo (2019) posits that “in order to create realistic entrepreneurship expectations among graduates, there is a need to have a subject that teaches entrepreneurship and how entrepreneurial skills can be sustained. Such subjects can be named Sustainable Entrepreneurship (SE)”. On the learning content, Jones et al, Fayolle, Gailly, and Lassas-Clerc in Olutuase, et al (2020) suggest that “continuous empirical inquiries should be carried out to determine how best entrepreneurship education programs should be designed and delivered to effectively stimulate desired outcome”. The components to build up entrepreneurial skills according to Ahmed et al in Ratten & Jones (2020) is “including course content (e.g. lecture material, guest speakers, online resources, modes of delivery etc) and course goals (e.g. learning introductory concepts and theory) compared to learning specific skills”. This approach will give individual student a direction on creating self confidence to venture into business.

Following the remarkable results from researches on the relevance of entrepreneurship education in producing skillful entrepreneurs, the inputs by Zeithaml and Rice in Kuratko (2004) maintain that

Education in entrepreneurship covered the entire scope of business administration...closest approach to the concept of management education, the field of study that takes a broad, integrative, pragmatic, rational approach to business to those who aspire to be entrepreneurs, managers, and top executives.

While there are substantial evidences that gave successful stories of renowned entrepreneurs that have no formal entrepreneurship education prior to their business status, yet entrepreneurship is seen as therapy to youth unemployment in academic forums (conferences etc). Undiel, et al (2012) observe that

Researchers anticipate further movement to reality where institutions of learning will begin to effectively take advantage of the paradigm shift to change the students’ mindsets so that the innate creative thinking of individuals will also begin to manifest in various trades and dexterity (Undiel, et al 2012, pp 282).

Principally, question raised is on the caliber of teachers to handle entrepreneurship, their expertise in imparting the required skills, mindset and other qualities expected of an entrepreneur. Many observers pose these and similar questions, including Undiel, et al (2021), thus

How is entrepreneurship education going to take off with the same caliber of teachers who have no form of entrepreneurial training at all? Will entrepreneurship Education commenced without entrepreneurial training centres? How can you teach entrepreneurial education when you are not an entrepreneur yourself?

Constructiveness of Entrepreneurial Education to Society as a Learning Concept

Job seeking is an innate trait in people especially the youth having ambitions to accomplish, but they recorded failure. Undiel, et al (2012) observe that Nigeria as a nation has continued to witness astronomical increase in job search among youth and graduates. A work to major and capital cities in Nigeria will speak volumes in this respect. This indicates that the teaching of entrepreneurial education in schools leaves much to be desired. This failure is not unconnected to lacking of the ability to identify, initiate and develop an enterprise due to deficiency of the entrepreneurial mind set and skills. Earlier North (2002) notes that there is an urgent need for young people to be educated and trained in the field of entrepreneurship in order for them to become job-creators rather than job-seekers. Students are trained to develop entrepreneurial skills to become creative and constructive members of their communities.

Academic institutions are knowledge and skills incubators; they designed modules to train individuals purposely and intentionally to prepare by remolding them in character and learning through entrepreneurship education, these institutions are the thinking tanks of the society. Entrepreneurship or entrepreneurial education has become matter of the moment and seen as solution to unemployment bothering people especially among youths. Ntaragwi (2021) opines that “entrepreneurship has become a staple in many conversations, strategies, and even practices in

many boardrooms, political meetings, and businesses. Earlier, North (2002) observes that “the establishment, promotion and cultivation of a culture of entrepreneurship among the youth are topic that has received considerable attention”. On this ground, he posits that “what if we saw entrepreneurship as a trait, a disposition, or as a skill and then link it to what and how we teach our students no matter their major”, therefore, how do we handle entrepreneurship in our institutions of learning? Do we consider teaching entrepreneurship or adopting training pedagogy as means of developing entrepreneurial skill and mindset to our students? Bawuah et al (2006) forward evidence that

Entrepreneurship training is critical to venture success...the skills traditionally taught in business schools are essential but not sufficient to make a successful entrepreneur...more attention needs to be paid to the development of their entrepreneurial skills, attributes and behaviours by introducing modules and courses specifically designed to develop in students the awareness and characteristics of the entrepreneur. (Bawuah, et al 2006, pp 3)

Purposely entrepreneurial training is expected at the end to change the mindset of the graduates to give them long-life learning opportunities. Experts extend scrutiny into entrepreneurship education, as indicated by Olutuase, Brijlal, & Yan, (2020) that “to what extent entrepreneurship education stimulates entrepreneurial skills is a question that has further extended the argument for or against the legitimacy of entrepreneurship education”. At some instances evidence shows positive result. Ratten & Jones in Ratten & Jones, (2020) posit that more recently this has changed due to more students interesting in acquiring knowledge about entrepreneurial behaviour that does not necessarily equate to starting a business...but as a way of getting students to think about future career directions; to entrepreneurial attitude with emphasis on a personal control over a situation that incorporates some degree of innovation”. However, others maintain the fact that inclusion of entrepreneurship education as learning concept impacted behavioural mindset in students with

entrepreneurial skill over those lacking, which justified that compulsory entrepreneurship course has impacted students' entrepreneurial skills (Olutuase et al, 2020).

Developing Entrepreneurial Competency and Mindsets among Students

The idea of fusing entrepreneurship education is to enable students during their school life to develop the skill of creating jobs and the mindset to pursue venture not only of their interest but within their area of study. Let them realize they can create or identify employment opportunity after graduation. This is instead of roaming or waiting idle waiting for job to come their way. Entrepreneurship has recently emerged as an incredible hawk, seen as embodying many economic developmental skills, and cutting through all disciplines including self-efficacy (Catherine, 2016). When people talk about business success, they talk about people who are entrepreneurs. One key shortcoming in teaching entrepreneurship in our institutions is training the skills that “allow one to observe a tool, a phenomenon, an activity, or an operation and see how it functions and how it can be improved (Ntaragwi, 2021).

Entrepreneurial development is determined by entrepreneurial intention. For every action to be accomplished is determined by the innate control. Entrepreneurial intention can only be built by intensive training. Nigerian students need skill to create intention, which is obtainable through entrepreneurial training. Nigerians are known as among the most enterprising people, however entrepreneurial activities have been mainly in the hands of the private and large informal sector operators” (Undiel, Sule and Bassey, 2012) which must graduates shun away from. This left our graduates at the back of national development economically by shunning away from local businesses opting for office or white collar jobs. The aspiration to address unemployment among graduates is by including entrepreneurship into educational curriculum to train and to make a pathway for them to have focus in life to widen their faculty beyond their academic qualifications.

Nigeria today needs innovative, well educated, and entrepreneurial citizens who, whatever their walks of life, have the spirit and inquisitiveness to think in new ways, and the courage to meet and adapt to the challenges facing them (Okeke & Edikpa, 2014). Therefore, higher institutions of learning need clear pathway on how to handle entrepreneurship as a learning concept in developing the mindset of the students for entrepreneurial skills.

Entrepreneurial Training and Skill Development

Entrepreneurial skills are skills needed that will help a student-entrepreneur in the process of designing, launching and running a new business, which is often initially a small business. The main goal of most entrepreneurial training is to develop some level of *entrepreneurial competencies*; which are defined as knowledge, skills and attitudes that affect the willingness and ability to perform the entrepreneurial job of new value creation. Lackéus (2015) reports views of scholars on Entrepreneurial education as often categorized into three approaches.

- a. Teaching “about” entrepreneurship, content-laden and theoretical approach giving a general understanding of the phenomenon. It is the most common approach in higher education institutions.
- b. Teaching “for” entrepreneurship means an occupationally oriented approach aiming at giving budding entrepreneurs the requisite knowledge and skills.
- c. Teaching “through” means a process based and often experiential approach where students go through an actual entrepreneurial learning process.

Despite the challenges identified by Smith et al in Lackéus (2015) “when trying to embed ‘teaching through’ into education, such as resource and time constraints, resistance from teachers, assessment challenges and cost implications, can be integrated into other subjects in general education, connecting entrepreneurial characteristics, processes and experiences to the core

subject” can be achieved. The embedded approach of “teaching through” entrepreneurship can be relevant to all students and on all levels of education.

Entrepreneurship is an individual’s ability to turn ideas into action. It includes creativity, innovation, and risk-taking, as well as the ability to plan and manage business venture. It is important to note that the possibility of developing entrepreneurial characteristics rest with the educational institutions that play key role, very early in the creation of knowledge and skills related to entrepreneurship. According to Herrity (2023)

Entrepreneurial skills can encompass a broad range of various skill sets like technical skills, leadership and business management skills and creative thinking. Because entrepreneurial skills can be applied to many different job roles and industries, developing your entrepreneurial skills can mean developing several types of skill sets.

Entrepreneurial skills help to build the competencies required by entrepreneur and are equally important for any potential entrepreneur. They include soft and hard skills and are basic from the following areas

- a. Business management skills
- b. Teamwork and leadership skills
- c. Communication and listening
- d. Customer service skills
- e. Financial skills
- f. Analytical and problem-solving skills
- g. Critical thinking skills
- h. Strategic thinking and planning skills
- i. Technical skills
- j. Time management and organizational skills
- k. Branding, marketing and networking skills (Herrity, 2023)

Entrepreneurial education for entrepreneurial skill development needs training pedagogy rather than teaching methodology. However, teaching and training can be combined to create

comprehensive learning experiences that integrate both knowledge acquisition and skill development, which is termed as Blended Learning Approaches, which combine traditional teaching methods with hands-on training activities that are now increasingly popular in educational and professional settings. According to Cornell Law School, Cornell University such training must develop the skills associated with entrepreneurship. Such skills may include, but are not limited to, the ability to:

- a. Take initiative;
- b. Creatively seek out and identify business opportunities;
- c. Develop budgets and forecast resource needs;
- d. Understand various options for acquiring capital and the trade-offs associated with each option; and
- e. Communicate effectively and market oneself and one's ideas.

To successfully develop entrepreneurial capabilities onto the students, institutions of learning have the responsibility to produce programmes and the implementation of learning methodologies to develop entrepreneurial skills; we need to think the needful by looking inward based on our settings and priorities. Alui & Ibe in Okeke & Edkpa (2014) are of the opinion that

Entrepreneurship education in Nigeria can only work if the prospects for improved productivity and local economic development are bright provided sustained attention is given to: provision of adequate infrastructure, support services and facilities for effective delivery; training, on sustainable basis, of all lecturers and instructors and provisions of access to adequate resources (including capital) to graduating students to enable them start their own business (pp 2).

At the end to meet up with demands of entrepreneurship skill training, Paul, & Ewubare, in Okeke & Edikpa (2014) observe that entrepreneurship lecturers, teachers/trainers should periodically be retrained and encouraged in the area of research to update their skills in order to be relevant in

today's era of dynamic and globalised environment. Additionally, the provision of entrepreneurial training centers for entrepreneurial training not be using conventional classrooms.

Conclusion

In conclusion it is now clear that entrepreneurship or entrepreneurial education is for entrepreneurial development, hence it is more to training than to teaching. Teaching is more concern with knowledge comprehension, understanding, and conceptual learning. Whereas training is about developing specific skills, competencies, and practical knowledge required for performing tasks, jobs. Therefore, considering the key objectives of entrepreneurial training, which are to acquire skills and mindset that will guide graduates in discovering, exploiting, initiating, developing and sustaining their own business venture and build in characteristics including perseverance, risk taking, patience and persistence. Entrepreneurial education should be delivered through training. These values are not obtainable via classroom teaching but practical training via activity-based approach using student-centered learning method.

Recommendations

Following the discussion so far it is recommended that higher institutions of learning in Nigeria should accept the challenges associated with entrepreneurship education that conventional classroom teaching is not suitable for entrepreneurial training. By that

- a. Vocational training centres should be upgraded to entrepreneurial centers to promote the acquisition of entrepreneurial competence by those seeking vocational skills.
- b. Entrepreneurial training modules should be design to all final year students for the period of six (6) to twelve (12) months before graduation across all departments/faculties during which every students will undergo rigorous entrepreneurial training.

- c. Lecturers and instructors should be having continuous training and retraining on entrepreneurship, because non-entrepreneurial instructor cannot deliver.
- d. Institutions need collaboration with financial institutions like banks, insurance companies, stock brokers, seasoned entrepreneurs to deliver lectures to the students and should be assessed based on the lecture.
- e. Excursions should be designed to places like Business Incubation Centers, export processing offices, NEXIM bank, Bank of Industry, Bank of Agriculture and industries. This will help the students to discover entrepreneurial opportunities.
- f. Students should be made to study a venture to identify lapses to which they should come up with live solution. This is one of the key methods for entrepreneurial development i.e. discovering new, or improving/modifying existing venture.
- g. Lastly, each student must come up with feasibility report on live business for assessment where possible by expert in business management upon which passing overall activities will determine student's graduation.
- h. Students Industrial Work Experience should be re-design to suit or enhance students' entrepreneurial skill development.
- i. There is need for more emphasis on collaboration with industries and business outfit for entrepreneurship training.

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